

A STUDY ON THE WORKING CONDITIONS AND OCCUPATIONAL PROBLEMS OF TAXI DRIVERS IN MANGALORE CITY

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Abstract

Taxi drivers are susceptible to many types of problems and issues. The major problems faced by them include unpredictability of pay, long hours of work and health related problems. The customers perceive that the only thing they have to do is drive around and give rides, but even though this job is simple in theory, the day-to-day working conditions of these taxi drivers are actually quite stressful. In order to find out the intricacies of the work life of the taxi drivers of Mangalore city, this study is conducted. The research design adopted by the investigator is exploratory and descriptive in nature. Accidental sampling technique was used for the selection of the respondents. A structured interview schedule was used to elicit the required information. The results of the study reveal that the respondents develop pain on the body, sleeplessness and eyesight related problems due to the nature of their work. They also have developed bad habits like drinking, smoking or tobacco chewing. Road accidents and lack of safety were considered the major occupational risk by the respondents. The study also points out that few respondents also have faced problems from police and other law enforcement authorities. Competition from their own co-workers was also felt by some of the respondents. The study suggests that there is a need for sensitizing general public about the working condition and work life of the taxi drivers. It also suggests that awareness programs need to be conducted among this group also about health, safety and security of life.

Keywords: Taxi drivers, work life, health, habits, sensitization and Working conditions.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Prevalence of a good urban transportation system can ease a lot of other urban problems like housing, shopping centers and industrial locations. On the contrary lack of it could accentuate the problems to a greater degree. Urban transport of Udupi is exceptional in several ways to that of other cities of the state, and without exaggeration of the country. For a city of Udupi size and economy the city bus services both private and public are really extra ordinary. But it does not mean that Udupi city bus services are beyond reproach and problems. Taxis are very less in number. This is due to small geographical area of Udupi, as also due to cheap and efficient transport provided first by the city buses and secondly by auto rickshaws. As a large number of passengers do not use taxis in the urban transportation of the Udupi, their

study is eliminated by most researchers. But we should hasten to add that in Udupi taxis especially private taxis are playing highly appreciable role in the short distance inter-city transport of Udupi. They travel between Mangalore-Udupi, Udupi-Manipal; Udupi-Kundapur-Batkal is highly facilitated by these bank financed private taxis. Due to petrol price hike these taxi drivers are facing their own problems. This intercity taxi service deserves a separate study of its own.

2. WORKING CONDITIONS OF THE TAXI DRIVER:

Industrialization and urbanization brought about the migration of a large number of the people from village to towns. As job opportunities increased, the number of workers too increased in these areas. This naturally brought about an increased demand for traffic. Hence a good number of people find it advantage to take driving as their profession and become taxi drivers. Good drivers are familiar with streets in the areas they serve so they can choose the most efficient route to destinations and avoid traffic. They know the locations of frequently requested destinations, such as airports, bus and railroad terminals, convention centers, hotels, and other points of interest. In case of emergency, drivers should know the location of fire and police stations, as well as hospitals. Taxi drivers are under a lot of stress during their shift being a taxi cab driver sounds like an easy gig. After all, the only things they have to do is drive around and give people rides, But even though this job is simple in theory, the day-to-day working conditions of cab drivers are actually quite stressful.

3. CHALLENGES:

Pay is Unpredictable: Taxi drivers do not earn a regular paycheck or an hourly wage. Instead, they are paid based on the number of fares they get. Drivers usually use a meter to charge their customers based on time and distance, and one trip counts as a single fare. Since the number of fares a driver might get in one day can vary greatly, a taxi driver is never sure of how much money he'll make.

Long Hours and Limited Mobility: Not only do taxi drivers work eight-hour to 12-hour shifts, they also move very little during the day. Cab drivers sit in their seats for almost their entire shift; because they need to pick up as many fares as possible, some only get up to use the bathroom a few times during the day or to get gas. Taxi drivers don't even have to get up to eat, since they can use fast food drive-thru windows without having to stop the taxi.

Negative Effects on Health: Speaking of fast food, taxi cab drivers are prone to health problems due to their diets and limited movement. They are prone to heart problems, musculoskeletal and digestive system disorders, hemorrhoids, and fatigue. Many cab drivers have obesity too.

Crime: Taxi drivers are susceptible to many types of crime. Robbery is common, and drivers can also be victims of things such as murder, rape, car thefts, and hit-and-run accidents. Because cab drivers are constantly on the go, they are easy targets for criminals. Vehicle break downs, adverse weather, and other traffic risks are also faced by them.

Employment Change: Because the demand for taxi services is very sensitive to economic cycles, drivers may see declining demand for their services during economic downturns. Taxi drivers who work for private companies or individuals may face layoffs or reduced hours during times of economic distress. Opportunities fluctuate significantly with the overall

movements of the economy, because the demand for transportation depends on business travel and tourism.

4. METHODOLOGY:

The investigator has met with a few of the taxi drivers of Mangalore city and found that most of them spend a great deal of time away from their homes, usually eating their meals in hotels. Under such conditions it is likely that this particular section of the community would have certain needs and problems. Thus to conduct a study on the working conditions and its related problems was considered necessary, so as to attempt to evolve plans for the amelioration of their conditions. This present study is the result of an ardent desire on the part of the investigator to find out the real work-life conditions of taxi drivers, so as to provide suggestions for their improvement.

Aim: The main aim of the study was to understand the working conditions and problems of taxi drivers in Udupi. And the objectives are: To study the personal profile of the respondents; To find out the problems faced by taxi drivers in relation to their job-pertaining to relationship with commuters, co-workers and law enforcing authorities; To examine the socio-economic conditions of taxi drivers; To study their health problems; and to find ways and means to improve their work and service life situation.

Materials and Method: The research design adopted by the investigator is exploratory and descriptive. This research design suits the present study as the investigator tried to explore their problems with regard to their working conditions and problems. For this study, the investigator has made use of accidental or convenience sampling technique. According to this study system, a sample is selected according to the convenience of the researcher, considering the nature of the respondents' work, that their services are asked by the public at any time and having no fixed hours of work or leisure time, made it necessary for the investigator to choose accidental or convenience sampling technique. An interview schedule was the principal tool in collecting the necessary data. The schedule was administered by personal interviews with the respondents. The interviews were conducted at bus stands, on the road sides, near hotels, where the respondents could be available, while waiting for their passengers.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The data analysis of the study reveals certain significant aspects, which are termed to be the major finding of the study. It has been found that 34percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 31-40 years of age. Another finding reveals that a certain group of taxi drivers are above the age of 70 years. Majority (64percent) of the respondents are Hindus. Majority (82percent) of the respondents are part of nuclear families. There is considerable number of the employees who belongs to joint families too. Majority (46percent) of the respondents have acquired general or formal education. None of the respondents were illiterate. The study reveals that 76 percent of the respondents were married and 2 percent of the respondents were widowers. Findings reveal that the average number of members in each of the respondents' families is 4-6. Majority 44 percent of the respondents' spouses were housewives. The study clearly shows that 36 percent of them do not have any children and 34 percent of them have 2 children. The investigator has found that the total monthly income of all respondents is above Rupees 3000. While 32 percent of the respondents' families earn Rupees 20001-30000, 26

percent of the respondents' families earn Rupees 10001-20000. The study shows that a majority (32percent) of the taxi drivers have worked in similar jobs before taking up this profession, like auto rickshaw drivers, bus drivers, etc. Some of the respondents have been taxi drivers and not held any other type of profession. Majority (76percent) of respondents had below 10yrs of experiences in their previous jobs and 14percent of the respondents have between 11-20yrs of experience, as made known in this study.

Duration of Present Job and Earning from the Present Job: Every individual is expected to be committed to the jobs that they perform. Certain jobs are sought after for the payment received while certain others are undertaken out of personal interest. When a person takes up a job only on the basis of pay, it is highly possible that if encountered with an opportunity to earn more he/she will move on to such jobs. (*Table 1: Duration of present Job*)

The above data indicates the duration of present job and salary of present job, the majority of

Duration of present job	Earning from the present job			
	5000-10000	10001-15000	15001-20000	TOTAL
Below 10YRS	12 (38.71%)	19 (61.29%)	0	31 (100%)
11-20YRS	4 (36.36%)	5 (45.46%)	2 (18.18%)	11 (100%)
21-30YRS	2 (50%)	2 (50%)	0	4 (100%)
31-40YRS	0	2 (100%)	0	2(100%)
41-50YRS	2 (100%)	0	0	2(100%)
TOTAL	20 (40%)	28 56%)	2 (4%)	50(100%)

the respondents (62%) were having 1month to10 years of experience, 22 percent of them were experienced 11 to 20yrs and 8percent of the respondents were experienced 21-30 years and Four percent respectively were experienced 31-40yrs and 41-50years. Majority of the respondents (56%) were earning Rupees 10001-15000 per month whereas 20 respondents (40%) of them were earning only up to Rupees 5000-10000 per month and remaining two percent of them were earning 15001-20000 Rupees per month. Further a vast majority of the respondents (62%) have an experience of 1month to10years and these taxi drivers are earning Rupees 10001-15000per month. A contradiction is observed in the study is that the drivers having an experience of one month to 10 years were earning more income than the experienced drivers with more than 10years of experience. It draws a conclusion that the income earned may or may not depend on the years of experience of the taxi drivers.

Distribution of Health Related Problems and Handling Health Problems: Taxi driving is not just as easy as it seems. It involves a lot of concentrations and stiff body control the frequency of stress, working condition etc leading to body ailments like pains and aches, sleeplessness and so on. The job also involves a lot of commitment and working hard at times, especially during the seasons, one cannot afford to take rest at home for several reasons like loan, debt, expenses at home, dependents etc. (*Table 2:Health related problem and handling health related problem*)

Health problems	Handling Health Related Problem			
	Nothing till now	Taking Rest	Treatment	Total
Nothing till now	27 (100%)	0	0	27(100%)
Pains and Aches	0	3 (23.07%)	10 (76.92%)	13 (100%)
Sleeplessness	0	5 (100%)	0	5(100%)
Eye Sight	0	0	5(100%)	5(100%)
Total	27 (54%)	8 (16%)	15 (30%)	50 (100%)

The above table shows the health problem faced by the respondents and measures taken for handling them. It is learnt that 27 respondents who forms the majority have not faced health problem till now due to their job and this corresponds with the majority of 27 taxi drivers who say that they have not taken any measures of handling health problems. While 13 respondents experience pains and aches, further 5 taxi drivers have suffered from sleeplessness because of the nature of their job and 5 respondents have developed eye sight related problems. Of the 23 respondents, 15 respondents have availed treatment of some sort and 8 taxi drivers have preferred to take rest to solve their health problems.

Opinion about Habits Developed: Sometimes due to stress, bad company kept among colleagues one tends to develop socially unacceptable habits or bad habits that can lead to several problems related to social, personal, health and finance.

DIAGRAM NO: 1a

The above graphs reveals that 50percent of the respondents (25) have not developed any bad habits in their period of working, whereas 20percent of the respondents (10) started tobacco chewing as taxi drivers since they were sometimes required to work during night shifts and tobacco keeps them from falling asleep and 16percent of the respondents developed smoking habits and 14percent of them developed drinking habit in their work life. Along with all these

some respondents have also developed habits of intermingling with the other taxi drivers, making friends' which tends to bring unity among all the taxi drivers.

Job Related Risks: The risks faced by the taxi drivers are immense. Bad roads are the cause for several fatal accidents and deaths, bad street lighting, environmental conditions like landscape, heavy rainfall or even uprooted trees fallen on roads cause major risks. At times technical problem like vehicle breakdowns, tire punctures is also possible.

DIAGRAM NO: 2a

The above line graph reveals that the job related risks faced by the respondents in respect to their job. Here 44 percent of the respondents believe road accidents were the biggest risk, while 38percent of the respondents have not come across any risks from the beginning up till now whereas 16 percent of the respondents consider lack of safety to be risky especially during vehicle breakdowns, use of the car for robbery by customers. No job is risk free, be it the nature of the job or any other feature that is concerned with the job like travelling and so on. In a job concerned with transportation, safety on road becomes the biggest cause of anxiety, for both passengers and drivers.

6. OTHER PROBLEMS:

The investigator has found out that 22percent of the respondents face problems of competition from co-workers whereas 62percent of the respondents said they have no such problem. A majority (84percent) of the respondents does not face problems from law enforcement authorities but 8percent respondents reported that they are at times subjected to unnecessary inspection by the police and have been asked to pay fines for reasons like not wearing uniforms and so on. A majority (84percent) of the respondents does not face problems from law enforcement authorities but 8percent respondents reported that they are at times subjected to unnecessary inspection by the police and have been asked to pay fines for reasons like not wearing uniforms and so on. A relatively small percentage that is 20percent of respondents has a problem with the Road Transport Officer for high payment of taxes.

7. SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Man has been working since time immemorial. The urge to work seems to be deep rooted in most men and work is viewed as much more than a means of seeking economic gratification.

- 1) There is a need for sensitizing the general public towards taxi drivers and the work they perform.
- 2) Awareness among the general public has to be created to treat the taxi drivers as human beings and not as the slaves while hiring the taxi and to respect and co-operate with the taxi drivers for ensuring better hospitality and services from them.
- 3) Awareness among the taxi drivers should be created so that they can develop a friendly and humane approach towards the customers in order to deal with them effectively.
- 4) Taxi drivers need to be sensitized about the legal provisions and the legal compliances.
- 5) They need to form associations through which they can take better actions on tackling problems they face, especially during night shifts like lack of proper road lights, bad roads, etc by appealing as a whole to the competent authorities.
- 6) There should be proper co-ordination between the government authorities (like Police, Road Transportation Officer) to ensure smooth functioning of the taxi drivers profession.
- 7) In order to prevent exploitation by the government officials there should be measures imposed in order to bring about transparency in the system.

9. CONCLUSION

The study successfully brings to fore beyond doubt, the working conditions and problems of the taxi drivers in Mangalore city. Taxi driving as a profession is not much important today as it is believed to be a job that a person would take up as a last resort and not as career. However taxi drivers do form an important part of the professional world, for everyone requires their transportation facility at one point of time or the other. They too face lot of constraints in the course of their work. It includes problems of night shift, transport authorities and whole lot of physical ailments. This study has made an attempt to bring to light the general work conditions of taxi drivers in Mangalore city and the problems they face while on duty. The Major risk they face from their profession is fear of accidents. It is important that there should be some sort of training and awareness programs conducted for these drivers so that, they can manage the hardships of life.

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